

Original Set n = 214 *			Revised Set n = 148	Test Set ≤ 4 CD4 AND ≤ 4 CD8 T cell responders n =109			Identity Set ≥ 98% sequence identify n = 61		Affinity-HLA Set High affinity binding to most HLA alleles n = 35			Final Set High immunogenicity n = 24	
HCMV Protein	Gene Bank or Swiss Prot ID	Reason for exclusion from Revised Set	HCMV Protein	HCMV Protein	CD8 (#)	CD4 (#)	HCMV Protein	Sequence identity (median %)	HCMV Protein	Peptides with IC50 ≤50nM (#)	Restricting HLA alleles (#)	HCMV Protein	Immunogenicity score (median) †
UL 4	CAA35437		UL 4	UL 4	1	4	UL4	88.7					
UL 5	CAA35438		UL 5	UL 5	0	0	UL5	97					
UL 6	CAA35439		UL 6	UL 6	0	0	UL6	85.2					
UL 7	CAA35440		UL 7	UL 7	1	0	UL7	87.8					
UL 8	CAA35441	NFL											
UL 9	CAA35442		UL 9	UL 9	0	1	UL9	58.6					
UL 10	CAA35443		UL 10	UL 10	0	0	UL10	95.3					
UL 11	CAA35444		UL 11	UL 11	0	1	UL11	71.7					
UL 12	CAA35446	ASO											
UL 13	CAA35445		UL 13	UL 13	0	3	UL 13	98.1	UL 13	149	20		
UL 14	CAA35447		UL 14	UL 14	1	0	UL 14	99.1	UL 14	70	18		
UL 15	CAA35415	ASO											
UL 16	CAA35448		UL 16	UL 16	1	4	UL 16	98.3	UL 16	81	18		
UL 17	CAA35416		UL 17	UL17	0	5							
UL 18	CAA35417		UL 18	UL 18	1	4	UL 18	97.4					
UL 19	CAA35418		UL 19	UL 19	0	0	UL 19	98	UL 19	50	15		
UL 20	CAA35419		UL 20	UL 20	0	3	UL 20	86.5					
UL 21	CAA35420	ASO											
UL 21.5	P16845		UL 21.5	UL 21.5	1	2	UL21.5	87.5					
UL 22	CAA35421	ASO											
UL 23	CAA35422		UL 23	UL 23	3	1	UL 23	98.9	UL 23	116	20		
UL 24	CAA35423		UL 24	UL 24	1	5							
UL 25	CAA35424		UL 25	UL 25	1	9							
UL 26	CAA35425		UL 26	UL 26	2	0	UL 26	98.9	UL 26	44	20		
UL 27	CAA35426		UL 27	UL 27	0	1	UL 27	98.7	UL 27	186	23	UL 27	0.086
UL 28	CAA35427	COMB	UL 28/UL29	UL 28/UL29	10	4							
UL 29	CAA35428												
UL 30	CAA35429		UL 30	UL 30	0	0	UL30	96.7					
UL 31	CAA35430		UL 31	UL 31	0	1	UL 31	99.2	UL31	201	20		
UL 32	CAA35431		UL 32	UL 32	9	13							
UL 33	CAA35432*		UL 33	UL 33	6	1							
UL 34	CAA35393		UL 34	UL 34	5	0							

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HCMV Protein	Gene Bank or Swiss Prot ID	Reason for exclusion from Revised Set	HCMV Protein	HCMV Protein	CD8 (#)	CD4 (#)	HCMV Protein	Sequence identity (median %)	HCMV Protein	Peptides with IC50 ≤50nM (#)	Restricting HLA alleles (#)	HCMV Protein	Immunogenicity score (median) †
UL 65	CAA35380	ASO											
UL 66	CAA35381	ASO											
UL 67	CAA35382	ASO											
UL 68	CAA35383	ASO											
UL 69	CAA35384		UL 69	UL 69	8	6							
UL 70	CAA35386		UL 70	UL 70	0	2	UL 70	99.6	UL 70	341	25	UL 70	0.097
UL 71	CAA35385		UL 71	UL 71	2	2	UL 71	99.2	UL 71	82	16		
UL 72	CAA35387		UL 72	UL 72	0	0	UL 72	99.0	UL 72	104	23	UL 72	0.055
UL 73	CAA35388		UL 73	UL 73	0	0	UL 73	79.0					
UL 74	CAA35389		UL 74	UL 74	0	0	UL 74	80.3					
UL 75	CAA35390		UL 75	UL 75	4	8							
UL 76	CAA35391		UL 76	UL 76	0	1	UL76	97.9					
UL 77	CAA35392		UL 77	UL 77	3	0	UL77	97.8					
UL 78	CAA35351		UL 78	UL 78	3	5							
UL 79	CAA35352		UL 79	UL 79	0	1	UL 79	99.7	UL 79	96	19		
UL 80	CAA35353		UL 80	UL 80	0	1	UL 80	98.2	UL 80	114	22	UL80	-0.059†
UL 80A	CAA35354	NFL											
UL 81	CAA35355	ASO											
UL 82	CAA35356		UL 82	UL 82	6	8							
UL 83	CAA35357		UL 83	UL 83	19	24	UL83	99.5	UL83	137	22	UL83	0.076
UL 84	CAA35358		UL 84	UL 84	2	0	UL 84	98.5	UL 84	130	23	UL 84	0.066
UL 85	CAA35359		UL 85	UL 85	1	2	UL 85	99.7	UL 85	105	23	UL85	-0.014†
UL 86	CAA35360		UL 86	UL 86	6	22							
UL 87	CAA35361		UL 87	UL 87	3	4	UL 87	99.6	UL 87	328	23	UL 87	0.045
UL 88	CAA35362		UL 88	UL 88	1	0	UL 88	99.8	UL 88	148	24	UL 88	0.091
UL 89	CAA35363		UL 89	UL 89	0	3	UL 89	99.4	UL 89	242	24	UL 89	0.071
UL 90	CAA35364	ASO											
UL 91	CAA35365		UL 91	UL 91	3	0	UL 91	98.2	UL 91	34	9		
UL 92	CAA35366		UL 92	UL 92	0	0	UL 92	99.5	UL 92	103	24	UL 92	0.043
UL 93	CAA35367		UL 93	UL 93	0	0	UL 93	98.7	UL 93	172	21	UL 93	0.115
UL 94	CAA35368		UL 94	UL 94	8	1							
UL 95	CAA35369		UL 95	UL 95	0	0	UL 95	99.1	UL 95	150	23	UL95	0.004†

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UL 96	CAA35370		UL 96	UL 96	0	0	UL 96	98.4	UL 96	12	6	UL97 UL98	0.011† 0.027†					
UL 97	CAA35333		UL 97	UL 97	0	0	UL 97	99.4	UL 97	174	22							
UL 98	CAA35334		UL 98	UL 98	2	0	UL 98	99.5	UL 98	224	24							
UL 99	CAA35335		UL 99	UL 99	5	18	UL100	97.5	UL100	79	17							
UL100	CAA35336		UL100	UL100	3	4												
UL101	CAA35337	ASO	UL103	UL103	2	0												
UL102	CAA35338	NFL																
UL103	CAA35339																	
UL104	CAA35341																	
UL105	CAA35340																	
UL106	CAA35342	ASO																
UL107	CAA35343	ASO																
UL108	CAA35344	ASO																
UL109	CAA35347	ASO																
UL110	CAA35348	ASO																
UL111	CAA35349	ASO																
UL111A	CAA35350	NFL																
UL112	P16768	NFL																
UL113	CAA35315		UL113	UL113	2	14	UL114	99.6	UL114	79	17							
UL114	CAA35316		UL114	UL114	3	3												
UL115	P16832		UL115	UL115	0	3												
UL116	CAA35318		UL116	UL116	4	1												
UL117	CAA35319		UL117	UL117	1	0												
UL118	CAA35320	COMB	UL118/119	UL118/119	0	1												
UL119	CAA35321																	
UL120	CAA35322																	
UL121	CAA35323		UL121	UL121	0	0						UL121	95.0	UL123	115	21	UL123	-0.108†
UL122	P19893		UL122	UL122	12	15												
UL123	CAA35325		UL123	UL123	18	12	UL123	97.2										
UL124	CAA35326		UL124	UL124	1	0	UL124	96.1										
UL125	CAA35327	ASO	UL126	UL126														
UL126	CAA35328	ASO																

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HCMV Protein	Gene Bank or Swiss Prot ID	Reason for exclusion from Revised Set	HCMV Protein	HCMV Protein	CD8 (#)	CD4 (#)	HCMV Protein	Sequence identity (median %)	HCMV Protein	Peptides with IC50 ≤50nM (#)	Restricting HLA alleles (#)	HCMV Protein	Immunogenicity score (median) †
US 5	CAA35272	ASO											
US 6	CAA35273		US 6	US 6	0	2	US6	95.6					
US 7	CAA35274		US 7	US 7	0	1	US7	95.1					
US 8	CAA35275		US 8	US 8	1	2	US8	97.8					
US 9	CAA35276		US 9	US 9	1	1	US 9	98.8	US9	103	19		
US10	CAA35277		US10	US10	2	3	US10	98.4	US10	52	17		
US11	CAA35278		US11	US11	1	0	US11	98.6	US11	105	23	US11	0.087
US12	CAA35279		US12	US12	3	3	US12	98.9	US12	162	21	US12	0.091
US13	CAA35280		US13	US13	0	0	US13	99.6	US13	169	21	US13	0.132
US14	CAA35281		US14	US14	2	1	US14	97.4					
US15	CAA35282 (amino acids 223-484)*		US15	US15	0	2	US15	99.6	US15	148	21	US15	0.096
US16	CAA35283		US16	US16	2	3	US16	99.4	US16	179	21	US16	0.130
US17	CAA35284		US17	US17	0	2	US17	99.7	US17	149	20		
US18	CAA35285		US18	US18	2	5							
US19	CAA35286		US19	US19	1	2	US19	98.3	US19	138	19		
US20	P09724		US20	US20	2	2	US20	99.6	US20	169	22	US20	0.025†
US21	CAA35288		US21	US21	0	1	US21	97.9					
US22	CAA35289		US22	US22	1	7							
US23	CAA35290		US23	US23	2	6							
US24	CAA35291		US24	US24	3	3	US24	99.6	US24	166	24	US24	0.103
US25	CAA35292	ASO											
US26	CAA35293		US26	US26	3	6							
US27	CAA35259		US27	US27	1	1	US27	96.9					
US28	P69332.1		US28	US28	1	0	US28	98.9	US28	208	26	US28	0.067
US29	CAA35261		US29	US29	10	0							
US30	CAA35262		US30	US30	5	1							
US31	CAA35263 (aa37-161)		US31	US31	0	1	US31	99.4	US31	44	12		
US32	CAA35264		US32	US32	11	1							
US33	CAA35266	ASO											
US34	CAA35265		US34	US34	0	1	US34	96.3					

Table A2. CD4 or CD8 T cell reactivities to Revised Set HCMV proteins sorted by A) participant number or B) number of proteins recognized by total T cells (CD4+CD8). Mean 25 and median 21 proteins were recognized. P, participants.

A)								B)							
P	CD4 <1%	CD4 >1%	CD8 <1%	CD8 >1%	Total CD4	Total CD8	Total CD4+CD8	P	CD4 <1%	CD4 >1%	CD8 <1%	CD8 >1%	Total CD4	Total CD8	Total CD4+CD8
P 1	5	0	16	8	5	24	29	P 32	3	1	0	2	4	2	6
P 2	8	2	2	1	10	3	13	P 26	5	0	2	0	5	2	7
P 3	11	0	2	0	11	2	13	P 5	7	0	1	0	7	1	8
P 4	25	3	15	2	28	17	45	P 16	2	0	3	3	2	6	8
P 5	7	0	1	0	7	1	8	P 31	0	3	5	1	3	6	9
P 6	25	4	8	4	29	12	41	P 27	6	0	4	0	6	4	10
P 7	6	2	8	6	8	14	22	P 12	2	2	4	3	4	7	11
P 8	23	3	5	1	26	6	32	P 2	8	2	2	1	10	3	13
P 9	20	9	12	6	29	18	47	P 3	11	0	2	0	11	2	13
P 10	15	3	4	0	18	4	22	P 20	5	0	6	2	5	8	13
P 11	10	0	2	3	10	5	15	P 11	10	0	2	3	10	5	15
P 12	2	2	4	3	4	7	11	P 24	9	3	4	0	12	4	16
P 13	9	0	8	3	9	11	20	P 30	1	6	6	4	7	10	17
P 14	6	1	7	4	7	11	18	P 14	6	1	7	4	7	11	18
P 15	14	3	3	1	17	4	21	P 13	9	0	8	3	9	11	20
P 16	2	0	3	3	2	6	8	P 22	9	5	3	3	14	6	20
P 17	13	2	8	0	15	8	23	P 15	14	3	3	1	17	4	21
P 18	16	3	10	3	19	13	32	P 7	6	2	8	6	8	14	22
P 19	31	4	19	6	35	25	60	P 10	15	3	4	0	18	4	22
P 20	5	0	6	2	5	8	13	P 17	13	2	8	0	15	8	23
P 21	11	7	15	5	18	20	38	P 23	12	4	6	4	16	10	26
P 22	9	5	3	3	14	6	20	P 1	5	0	16	8	5	24	29
P 23	12	4	6	4	16	10	26	P 29	0	2	20	7	2	27	29
P 24	9	3	4	0	12	4	16	P 8	23	3	5	1	26	6	32
P 25	25	2	16	1	27	17	44	P 18	16	3	10	3	19	13	32
P 26	5	0	2	0	5	2	7	P 21	11	7	15	5	18	20	38
P 27	6	0	4	0	6	4	10	P 6	25	4	8	4	29	12	41
P 28	29	2	23	0	31	23	54	P 25	25	2	16	1	27	17	44
P 29	0	2	20	7	2	27	29	P 4	25	3	15	2	28	17	45
P 30	1	6	6	4	7	10	17	P 9	20	9	12	6	29	18	47
P 31	0	3	5	1	3	6	9	P 33	16	4	26	4	20	30	50
P 32	3	1	0	2	4	2	6	P 28	29	2	23	0	31	23	54
P 33	16	4	26	4	20	30	50	P 19	31	4	19	6	35	25	60

Supplemental Table 3. BLASTP summary of Test Set proteins. Shaded cells indicate proteins excluded from the Test Set in the next step of the algorithm. (A) UL region proteins. (B) US region proteins.

A)										
	TRL1	IRS1	TRL12	TRL6	TRL10	TRL11	TRL13/14	UL1	UL2	UL4
Access #	CAA35449	CAA35311	CAA35460	CAA35454	CAA35458	CAA35459	CAA35461 CAA35433	CAA35434	CAA35435	CAA35436
Length (aa)	311	846	416	111	171	234	147 - 302	224	60	149 - 152
Min	76.53%	91.35%	33.72%	97.30%	90.06%	94.04%	41.46%	55.36%	90.00%	79.19%
Max	99.68%	99.76%	99.76%	100.00%	99.42%	99.57%	99.67%	99.55%	98.33%	100.00%
Mean	91.92%	95.13%	48.95%	98.57%	94.80%	96.40%	64.72%	82.54%	94.17%	90.89%
Median	92.28%	95.37%	44.81%	98.20%	94.74%	96.58%	63.97%	76.21%	93.33%	88.67%
	UL5	UL6	UL7	UL9	UL10	UL11	UL13	UL14	UL16	UL17
Access #	CAA35437	CAA35438	CAA35439	CAA35441	CAA35442	CAA35443	CAA35444	CAA35447	CAA35415	CAA35448
Length (aa)	166	280 - 284	222 - 324	228 - 235	258 - 259	275	473	327	230	104
Min	92.77%	77.42%	79.73%	50.21%	84.77%	65.94%	96.62%	98.17%	96.96%	97.12%
Max	99.40%	100.00%	99.55%	99.12%	99.61%	99.64%	99.79%	99.69%	99.57%	99.04%
Mean	96.08%	88.18%	87.43%	66.11%	93.26%	77.80%	98.23%	99.05%	98.34%	98.19%
Median	96.99%	85.21%	87.84%	58.55%	95.29%	71.74%	98.10%	99.08%	98.26%	98.08%
	UL18	UL19	UL20	UL21.5	UL23	UL24	UL25	UL26	UL27	UL28/29
Access #	CAA35416	CAA35417	CAA35418	CAA35419	CAA35420	P16845	CAA35424	CAA35425	CAA35426	CAA35428
Length (aa)	363 - 368	98	340	104-105	284	300 - 358	656	118	608	700
Min	94.29%	96.94%	74.78%	79.61%	97.89%	98.32%	99.09%	98.94%	97.86%	99.00%
Max	99.73%	98.98%	100.00%	99.03%	100.00%	100.00%	99.85%	99.47%	100.00%	99.86%
Mean	97.35%	98.16%	84.34%	88.87%	98.94%	99.35%	99.54%	99.04%	98.76%	99.51%
Median	97.55%	97.96%	86.51%	87.50%	98.94%	99.44%	99.54%	98.94%	98.68%	99.57%
	UL30	UL31	UL32	UL33	UL34	UL35	UL36	UL37	UL38	UL40
Access #	CAA35429	CAA35430	CAA35431	CAA35432*	CAA35393	CAA35394	CAA35395	CAA35396	CAA35397	CAA35399
Length (aa)	121	595	1,048	412	407	640	476	487	331	221
Min	94.21%	98.49%	98.00%	91.03%	98.77%	98.59%	91.99%	88.75%	96.68%	91.86%
Max	99.17%	99.66%	99.81%	99.49%	99.75%	99.84%	99.79%	99.79%	99.70%	99.55%
Mean	96.83%	99.15%	99.12%	94.95%	99.18%	99.35%	98.77%	91.78%	98.58%	96.57%
Median	96.69%	99.16%	99.24%	93.59%	99.26%	99.38%	98.95%	91.17%	98.64%	96.38%

	UL41A	UL42	UL43	UL44	UL45	UL46	UL47	UL48	UL48.5	UL49
Access #	CAA74073	CAA74074	CAA74075	CAA35403	CAA35404	CAA35405	CAA35406	CAA35407	YP_081507.1	CAA35408
Length (aa)	78	78	423	433	906	290	982	2,241	75	570
Min	98.72%	92.68%	98.35%	99.31%	98.68%	99.31%	99.19%	98.84%	97.33%	98.25%
Max	98.72%	99.20%	99.76%	99.77%	99.89%	99.66%	100.00%	99.55%	98.67%	99.82%
Mean	98.72%	94.97%	99.11%	99.59%	99.35%	99.63%	99.64%	99.28%	98.34%	98.95%
Median	98.72%	94.74%	99.05%	99.77%	99.45%	99.66%	99.69%	99.29%	98.67%	98.95%
	UL50	UL51	UL52	UL53	UL54	UL55	UL56	UL57	UL69	UL70
Access #	CAA35409	CAA35410	CAA35411	CAA35412	CAA35413	CAA35414	CAA35371	CAA35372	CAA35384	CAA35386
Length (aa)	397	361	668	375	1,242	906	850	1,235	744 - 748	946
Min	98.25%	96.95%	98.20%	97.39%	99.11%	92.00%	98.59%	98.87%	98.39%	99.26%
Max	99.75%	100.00%	99.85%	99.73%	100.00%	99.00%	99.88%	99.92%	99.73%	99.89%
Mean	99.18%	99.46%	99.34%	99.27%	99.55%	95.85%	99.39%	99.75%	99.05%	99.60%
Median	99.25%	99.45%	99.40%	99.47%	99.52%	95.00%	99.41%	99.76%	99.06%	99.58%
	UL71	UL72	UL73	UL74	UL75	UL76	UL77	UL78	UL79	UL80
Access #	CAA35385	CAA35387	CAA35388	CAA35389	CAA35390	CAA35391	CAA35392	CAA35351	CAA35352	CAA35353
Length (aa)	361	388	138	466	743	325	642	431	295	708
Min	96.68%	97.94%	71.74%	73.19%	95.69%	96.62%	96.57%	96.77%	98.98%	97.46%
Max	99.72%	99.74%	99.28%	99.79%	99.87%	99.69%	99.38%	100.00%	99.66%	99.86%
Mean	99.19%	98.80%	83.37%	83.06%	97.61%	97.95%	97.88%	98.48%	99.49%	98.42%
Median	99.17%	98.97%	78.99%	80.30%	96.77%	97.85%	97.82%	98.38%	99.66%	98.17%
	UL82	UL83	UL84	UL85	UL86	UL87	UL88	UL89	UL91	UL92
Access #	CAA35356	CAA35357	CAA35358	CAA35359	CAA35360	CAA35361	CAA35362	CAA35363	CAA35365	CAA35366
Length (aa)	559	561	586	306	1,370	941	429	674	111	201
Min	98.57%	97.68%	97.10%	99.35%	99.05%	97.56%	90.68%	98.66%	95.50%	98.51%
Max	99.82%	99.82%	99.83%	99.67%	99.93%	99.89%	100.00%	99.85%	99.10%	99.50%
Mean	99.42%	99.49%	98.52%	99.63%	99.66%	99.27%	99.40%	99.37%	97.77%	99.22%
Median	99.64%	99.47%	98.47%	99.67%	99.78%	99.57%	99.77%	99.41%	98.20%	99.50%
	UL93	UL94	UL95	UL96	UL97	UL98	UL99	UL100	UL103	UL104
Access #	CAA35367	CAA35368	CAA35369	CAA35370	CAA35333	CAA35334	CAA35335	CAA35336	CAA35339	CAA35341
Length (aa)	594	345	531	127	707	584	190	372	249	697
Min	97.47%	97.97%	93.93%	97.64%	98.30%	98.97%	90.05%	96.52%	99.20%	98.71%
Max	99.83%	99.71%	99.81%	99.21%	99.86%	99.83%	99.47%	99.73%	99.60%	99.86%
Mean	98.59%	98.61%	98.39%	98.25%	99.43%	99.39%	97.76%	98.12%	99.51%	99.63%
Median	98.65%	98.55%	98.68%	98.43%	99.43%	99.49%	97.89%	97.46%	99.60%	99.71%

	UL105	UL113	UL114	UL115	UL116	UL117	UL118/119	UL120	UL121	UL122
Access #	CAA35340	CAA35315	CAA35316	P16832	CAA35318	CAA35319	CAA35320 CAA35321	CAA35322	CAA35323	P19893
Length (aa)	956	684	250	603	603	424	346	201	180	411
Min	98.12%	98.39%	98.00%	97.48%	91.17%	98.82%	90.06%	77.72%	92.22%	96.84%
Max	99.90%	99.85%	100.00%	100.00%	99.68%	99.76%	99.71%	99.50%	99.44%	100.00%
Mean	99.69%	99.21%	99.46%	98.32%	95.45%	99.20%	95.49%	85.78%	95.13%	99.38%
Median	99.69%	99.27%	99.60%	98.20%	95.18%	99.29%	96.82%	84.58%	95.00%	99.76%
	UL123	UL124	UL130	UL132	UL133	UL134	UL135	UL136	UL137	UL138
Access #	CAA35325	CAA35326	CAA35332	CAA35295	AAA85872.1	AAA85873.1	AAA85874.1	1	AAA85876.1	AAA85877.1
Length (aa)	491	152	214	270	251	175	328	240	96	169
Min	94.09%	90.85%	97.20%	91.48%	89.15%	92.61%	97.26%	95.51%	93.8%	97.04%
Max	99.80%	99.34%	100.00%	99.63%	99.22%	96.02%	98.48%	99.58%	97.9%	99.41%
Mean	97.16%	96.60%	98.63%	94.47%	96.00%	94.53%	97.90%	97.76%	95.2%	98.35%
Median	96.95%	96.05%	98.60%	93.33%	96.12%	94.59%	97.87%	97.92%	94.8%	98.22%
	UL139	UL141	UL142	UL144	UL146	UL147	UL148	UL149		
Access #	1	1	AAA85881.1	AAA85883.1	AAA85885.1	AAA85886.1	AAA85887.1	1		
Length (aa)	135	338	306	176	117	159	316	122		
Min	59.85%	98.22%	80.26%	77.27%	57.26%	86.16%	97.78%	86.29%		
Max	99.26%	100.00%	97.06%	100.00%	99.15%	99.37%	99.68%	95.08%		
Mean	84.74%	99.01%	91.09%	87.19%	89.63%	90.90%	98.76%	91.33%		
Median	82.96%	98.82%	91.83%	82.95%	96.58%	89.94%	98.73%	90.98%		
B)										
	US1	US2	US3	US6	US7	US8	US9	US10		
Access #	CAA35312	CAA35313	CAA35314	CAA35273	CAA35274	CAA35275	CAA35276	CAA35277		
Length (aa)	156	199	186	182	225	227	247	185		
Min	98.71%	97.99%	94.62%	78.69%	91.56%	94.71%	95.55%	96.22%		
Max	99.36%	99.50%	99.46%	99.45%	99.56%	99.56%	99.60%	99.46%		
Mean	99.25%	99.24%	98.02%	95.39%	95.41%	97.66%	98.82%	98.20%		
Median	99.36%	99.50%	97.85%	95.63%	95.11%	97.80%	98.79%	98.38%		
	US11	US12	US13	US14	US15	US16	US17	US18		
Access #	CAA35278	CAA35279	CAA35280	CAA35281	(P09718.2)	CAA35283	CAA35284	CAA35285		
Length (aa)	215	281	261	310	262	309	293	274		
Min	98.14%	98.22%	98.85%	94.67%	98.47%	98.38%	98.29%	99.64%		
Max	99.53%	99.64%	99.62%	99.68%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%		
Mean	98.69%	98.95%	99.47%	97.60%	99.49%	99.21%	99.36%	99.67%		
Median	98.60%	98.93%	99.62%	97.42%	99.62%	99.35%	99.66%	99.64%		

	US19	US20	US21	US22	US23	US24	US26	US27		
Access #	CAA35286	P09724	CAA35288	CAA35289	CAA35290	CAA35291	CAA35293	CAA35259		
Length (aa)	240	254	239	576	592	500	603	362		
Min	95.83%	98.82%	97.53%	99.13%	99.16%	99.00%	98.51%	95.75%		
Max	100.00%	100.00%	99.58%	99.83%	99.83%	99.80%	99.83%	99.72%		
Mean	98.22%	99.44%	98.07%	99.48%	99.68%	99.54%	99.22%	97.35%		
Median	98.33%	99.61%	97.94%	99.48%	99.66%	99.60%	99.17%	96.88%		
	US28	US29	US30	US31	US32	US34				
Access #	P09704	CAA35261	CAA35262	CAA35263	CAA35264	CAA35265				
Length (aa)	354	462	349	161	183	163				
Min	97.74%	97.62%	95.13%	98.76%	98.36%	92.02%				
Max	99.72%	99.57%	99.71%	99.38%	99.45%	99.39%				
Mean	98.86%	98.79%	97.56%	99.29%	99.06%	96.12%				
Median	98.87%	98.70%	97.71%	99.38%	98.91%	96.32%				